

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MANYIKA****FIRST NAME: MORRIS****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In order to write effective academic essays, the following basic steps should be followed.

- Research the topic, Organize Ideas, Write, Reference, Edit and Hand In.¹**
- Research the topic, Write, Reference, Organize ideas, Edit and Hand In.
- Research the topic, Organize ideas, Reference, Hand in, Edit and Write.
- Organize ideas, Write, Hand in, Reference, Edit and Research the topic.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7-12.

2. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Explain why plagiarism *MUST* be avoided.

- It supports the writer of the of an essay to finish.
- It is wrong, unethical, serious academic offense and has serious consequences.²**
- It is acceptable in academics and has no consequences.
- It is another way of finding information.

3. There are two main types of research; *pure* and *applied*. Contrast *Pure* and *Applied* Research.

- Pure research is mainly done purely without practice.
- Applied and Pure research are conducted at the same time.
- Applied research addresses conceptual problems and any direct practical consequences while pure research addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.
- Pure research addresses a conceptual problem that does not have any direct practical consequences while applied addresses a conceptual problem that does have practical consequences.³**

² Ibid., 7-12.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

4. In order to develop a constructive research argument, a researcher needs to engage sources of information. Which of the following is one of the uses secondary sources?
- Provide original” materials that provide you with the “raw” data.
 - Provide data obtained through observation or experiment in many fields.
 - Provide current research findings and find other points of view.⁴**
 - Provide direct information on events.
5. The notes style and author-date style are two commonly used citation styles. The author-date style is used when...
- You signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference.⁵**
 - You signal that you have used a source by not placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference.
 - You signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence.
 - None of the above.

⁴ Ibid., 36.

⁵ Ibid., 142-145.

6. The Notes-Bibliography style plays a critical role in the referencing process. Which of the following is a correct way of writing a *Notes-Style* from multiple authors?
- ##. Author #1's First and Last Names and Author #2's Last and First Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Publisher's Name: Place of Publication, Date of Publication), page number.
 - ##. Author #1's Last and First Names and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), page number.
 - ##. **Author #1's First and Last Names and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication), Page Number.**⁶
 - ##. Author #1's Last and First Names and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Publisher's Name: Place of Publication, Date of Publication), page number.
7. Research Methodology is one of the main sections of a research proposal. One of the purposes of this section is to.
- Show how and in what ways you will go about conducting your study.**⁷
 - Show the literature reviewed to develop the proposal.
 - Give a summary of the dissertation.
 - Show the research findings, discussions, and conclusions.

⁶ Ibid., 150.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, (London: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 208-209.

8. The goal of theoretical research is to...

- Contribute new knowledge or extend current theory to a new area.**⁸
- Use knowledge to contribute directly to the understanding of a problem.
- Generate a solution for the problem.
- Conducting research.

9. Abbreviations are used in the English language to help the readers.

- Emphasize the main point.
- Easily find the meanings of words
- Reduce the longevity of some words and quick access to items being meant.**⁹
- Increase the longevity of words, sentences, and paragraphs.

10. What is a Style Guide?

- A means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent.**¹⁰
- A guide on how to develop styles of writing.
- A guide on how to reference.
- A list of styles on how to quote.

⁸ Ibid., 240.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2021), 44.
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 41.

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Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.